

DIDACTIC OPPORTUNITIES OF TEACHING HISTORY OF MEDICINE TO FOREIGN STUDENTS STUDYING IN HIGHER MEDICAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Komilov Nodirbek Bokijonovich

doctor of philosophy (PhD) in history, associate professor
Fergana Medical Institute of Public Health
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8163850>

Annotation. This article highlights the didactic possibilities of teaching the history of medicine to foreign students, and analyzes the possibility of developing their creative activity by teaching the history of medicine.

Keywords: operational activity, cognitive activity, pedagogical creativity, didactic opportunity, methodology, medical deontology, medical practice, organizational component.

Today, the use of modern means of technology, information, computer, multimedia, Internet, distance learning, unified information environment, and similar information and communication technologies for the meaningful organization of the educational process in medical universities is effective.

Nowadays, the need to study the scientific-theoretical foundations of didactic educational technologies and their application to educational processes in medical universities is becoming one of the urgent issues. Effective use of the achievements of science, technology and advanced technology according to the purpose, tasks, content, methodical requirements of imparting knowledge to students is one of the urgent problems facing today's education system. Didactic educational technologies help students to develop enthusiasm and interest in knowledge, solid mastery of knowledge, free use of it in practice, and lead to high efficiency.

In teaching the history of medicine, it is appropriate to choose educational technologies based on the didactic task of each lesson.

In the course of medical education, it is possible to use developing methods to train students as creative, creative thinkers in the teaching of the history of medicine. For example, solving non-standard problems related to the history of medicine, in which the student remembers and applies some new solution methods.

It is known that the formation of new directions for the professional activity of the future medical worker, the study of their didactic possibilities - the transition to the third generation standards in the medical education system and

the revision of the general methodology, specific methods and techniques of teaching are also required.

Integration of our country into the world community, integration processes in various fields of medicine are developing together with the development of scientific and intensive technologies.

The role of information and knowledge is increasing in all aspects of higher medical education and in all areas of social development. In the information society, knowledge and skills are becoming the highest values in the life of incon. In recent years, this type of education, which stimulates the intellectual and moral development of students of medical institutions of higher education, activates their potential and forms critical thinking, is becoming more and more widespread. In the framework of this type of training, the student manifests himself as an active part of the educational activity.

Pedagogical creativity is understood as a state of pedagogical activity, in which the content of the educational process is developed in a fundamentally new way, in its scientific organization and in solving practical problems. It assumes that the teacher has a set of creative qualities, activity, deep attention, observation, unusual thinking skills, abilities, research skills, among which initiative, rich imagination, creativity, creative approach to the analysis of educational situations, solving pedagogical problems occupy an important place. ensures the independence of judgments and conclusions. This leads to the formation of future doctors in the history of medicine on the basis of "pedagogical modeling" and "pedagogical design".

During the teaching of history of medicine to foreign students, we will highlight the unique features of the didactic model of developing their creative activity.

The didactic model is connected to the theorist of step-by-step development of creative mental activities and the theorist of problem-based education.

The first one directs students to consciously creative management of the process of acquiring knowledge, focusing on the active, independent development of thinking and intellectual culture.

The second one encourages creative thinking and self-development, because the student himself must solve the problem and find a new way of action. Based on this theory, students are focused on the heuristic and creative level of active knowledge.

For example, when a foreign student uses stimulation at different stages of studying the topic "Formation and development of the science of the history of medicine", the model performs different functions. First of all, it helps to define the contours of academic concepts and to determine their hierarchical, didactic connections. Then it gives an opportunity to more fully express the important connections, to reveal the pedagogical conditions for improving the creative activity of students, to illuminate the effectiveness of its elements and their interaction.

This didactic model helps to prevent conflicts between the objective need to develop the creative activity of foreign students in the educational process and insufficiently developed pedagogical conditions for its theoretical and academic implementation.

The reason for the didactic model structure of this form - as a condition for the development of creative activity of foreign students in the educational process, is shown separately. When revealing the goal of developing students' creative activity, we approach the work based on its creative potential. From the psychological and pedagogical point of view, the goal is related to the change in the organization of the process of assimilation of the educational content, which is not only a logical meaning, but also the introduction of new steps, mechanisms into the cognitive process. In this, the development of the creative and intellectual abilities of the society, the full use of the potential of each student is emphasized, and the main didactic goal is to help solve the current problems of the medical system by creating a school system for the development of the student's creative ability in the educational process, that is, by studying the science of the history of medicine, the student will be able to learn this in the future. analyzes the shortcomings and achievements of the system.

Based on the above, the following didactic tasks were determined in teaching the history of medicine:

- arming foreign students with reflective creative activities and techniques;
- development of creative thinking of foreign students;
- stimulation of cognitive activity of foreign students;
- students who have acquired new knowledge and their creative application.

While teaching the history of medicine to foreign students, it is important to pay special attention to their creative activity. For example, during the mastering of the topic "History of the development of medicine in the territory

of Uzbekistan in the Middle Ages", the opinions of foreign students about Eastern scholars, information about the positive aspects of their work, a motivational component is formed in their work, that is, the values and goals of future professional work, which are carried out in the context of creative mastering, in the educational process, a system of dominant motives is created, which represents a conscious attitude to one's professional development.

The cognitive component of creative activity is manifested in its various forms in the context of the modern educational process. This component includes the following knowledge:

- theoretical, including knowledge about the forms, principles, goals, content, ends and forms of creative activity;
- one of the three ways of knowing the essence of creative activity, which includes methodological, human relations with the surrounding world;
- technological, developing educational technologies and knowledge about their implementation.

In accordance with these criteria, the following levels of didactic activity were determined in the educational process:

The first level - (pact) is characterized by lack of interest in cognitive activity, lack of experiential and creative problem solving when faced with educational tasks that require long and large intellectual efforts. Cognitive activity is active, but cognitive motives are dominant emacs. They are designed to be modeled by the teacher.

The second level - (middle) this level belongs to the group of reproductively active students. When it comes to knowledge, it can memorize certain information; in activity - mastering ready-made techniques. In this case, cognitive activity is accompanied by positive emotions, but they do not arise from creativity. There is no direction for creative activity, the controlling role of the teacher is stuck.

The third level - (high) creative motivation begins to affect student activity. There is an interest in performing tasks creatively. This level is characterized by the development of creative active work skills in the process of self-education, self-awareness. This is due to the significant participation of the teacher in solving complex educational problems.

Therefore, didactic opportunities for the development of student activity are the main means of ensuring the camaraderie of the educational process.

References:

1. Caramiciu J, Arcella D, Desai MS. History of medicine in US medical school curricula // Anesth Hist, 2019. №1(4). -P.111-114.

2. Kidd MG, Connor JT. Striving to do good things: Teaching humanities in Canadian medical schools //Med Humanities, 2018. №29(1). -P.45-54.
3. Howell JD. An elective course in medical history//Academic Medicine, 2020. № 66 (11). -P.68-95.
4. Louis-Courvoisier M, Wenger A. How to make the most of history and literature in the teaching of medical humanities: the experience of the University of Geneva // Medical humanities, 2021. № 31(1). -P.51-54.

